

THE ROLE OF REFLECTIVE LEARNING IN YOUTH EDUCATION

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada yoshlar tarbiyasida refleksiv ta’limning o‘rni, refleksiv ta’lim o‘rganuvchilar (talabalar)ni mazmunli saboq olish uchun o‘z tajribalari, his-tuyg‘ulari va fikrlarini tanqidiy tekshirishga undaydigan tizimli amaliyot sifatida ilmiy jihatdan tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: refleksiv ta’lim, yoshlar, tarbiya, intellektual rivojlanishi, spetsifik, kognitiv yondashuv.

Аннотация. В статье научно анализируется роль рефлексивного образования в воспитании молодежи, которое представляет собой систематическую практику, побуждающую учащихся к критическому анализу своих переживаний, чувств и мыслей для осмысленного обучения.

Ключевые слова: рефлексивное образование, молодежь, образование, интеллектуальное развитие, специфический, когнитивный подход.

Abstract. The article scientifically analyzes the role of reflective education in the upbringing of youth which is a systematic practice that encourages students to critically analyze their experiences, feelings, and thoughts to learn meaningfully.

Keywords: reflective education, youth, education, intellectual development, specific, cognitive approach.

Although the notion of reflection is not a newly studied concept in the field of education, intellectual development of students based on it, socio-pedagogical problems related to a cognitive approach to specific topics - critical thinking and self-reflection in traditional educational institutions, the lack of student attention to self-analysis and individual approach to the given topic remains relevant. The teaching system of many educational institutions is primarily focused on memorization and regurgitation of information, and in most cases, in spite of students’ engaging in reflexive education by grouping the learners in a small teams or pair work and enhancing the given information to be developed professionally, to analyze it based on his/her own discover and experience, and only then to be able to apply the considered information in his practical work time is allotted.

This problem hinders the intellectual development of students, limits their ability to think critically and independently, and at the same time, if there is no opportunity to assess reflectively (approach) their experiences, feelings and thoughts, students themselves and may have limited and stereotyped - regurgitated knowledge in their attempts to gain a deeper understanding of the world around. The question arises, what is the reflexive education implied in the main problem that arises within the scope of the above student's specialty?

Reflection comes from the Late Latin *refleccio*, *re* meaning "back" and *flectere* meaning "to bend". In the English language, the word reflection was first observed in the works of Descartes and even Plato in the 14th century (Mann and Walsh, 2017), and the word was also defined and placed in Aristotle's discussions of ethics (Ransome, 2009). The meaning of the word reflection as "a reflection made after someone has changed his mind on a subject" was first mentioned in the

English Etymological Dictionary in the 1600s (Etymological Dictionary - <https://www.etymonline.com/word/reflection>).

Reflective learning is “the skill of experiential learning in which people tend to be the most deficient” (Duley, J. S., 1981) which is not a single faceted concept, but a generic term that acts as a shorthand description for a number of important ideas and activities (Duley, J. S., 1981), it is a required ingredient for success so that methods which are permanently successful in formal education . . . depend for their efficiency upon the fact that they go back to the type of situation which causes reflection. (Dewey, 1916:154). And it is a matter of indifference by what psychological means the subject matter for reflection is provided, observation, memory, reading, communication are all avenues for supplying data. (Dewey, 1916:157). This approach allows people to increase their understanding, challenge assumptions, and encourage personal and professional growth. As Mezirow, J. (1997) and Schön, (1983) state reflection and learning are deeply intertwined with each other and reflections are central in integrating theoretical and practical competencies, as well as to raise awareness around implicit assumptions (Mezirow, 1997; Schön, 1983). Later Moon (1999) describes it as a mental processing method in which there is not an obvious solution, it is a purpose and/or an anticipated outcome that is applied to relatively complicated or unstructured ideas (p. 98).

According to Zuber-Skerritt, reflection was later defined as "the interconnectedness and integration of theory and practice, research and development, thought and action, rather than separation" (Zuber-Skerritt, 2001. 15- page). David Bowd, Rosemary Keogh and David Walker evaluated reflection as a general term that serves as a shorthand description of a number of important ideas and actions rather than a one-sided concept (David Boud, Rosemary Keogh and David Walker, 1985, 1987, 1994). In more general terms, reflection is important for interpreting and internalizing academic activity (Karm, 2010), and it serves as a way of questioning and sharing underlying assumptions, and improving team performance (Gordijn, Eernstman, Helder, & Brouwer, 2018.)

The contribution of experiential learning and its central role in individual learning and personal growth have been widely discussed across disciplines. Reflection has also long been interpreted as a process necessary to unleash the complex and rich learning potential of experience (eg, Boud et al., 1985; Harvey et al., 2010). Schön (1983) describes his research on reflection as "reflection provides a means by which experience can be understood and generalized during and after action." Nevertheless, thinking is one of the most widely used pedagogical tools in education, and although its use is widely emphasized, much of the literature lacks solid empirical support or a clear theoretical basis for thinking (Harvey et al., 2010).

Taken as a whole, reflective learning involves going beyond surface-level observations and learning about the underlying motivations, misconceptions, and assumptions that more deeply shape learner actions and decisions, and developing based on these mistakes and shortcomings.

The findings of this study support the idea that the stages of reflective learning typically include:

1. Description. This step involves describing the experience or situation the learner is thinking of, providing details of what happened, who was involved, and relevant context.

2. Emotions. This stage explores the student's emotional response to an experience or situation, how they felt at the time, and how those feelings influenced the student's actions or thoughts.

3. Evaluation. During this period, the student critically analyzes an experience or situation, which includes analyzing his or her own and other students' activities. (You evaluate what went well, what didn't, and why.)

4. Analysis. At this stage, the student examines the results and causes of experiments, considering the factors that lead to success or failure, taking into account the resulting trends.

5. Summary. This stage involves synthesizing and drawing conclusions from the learner's thoughts to identify key ideas, lessons learned, or lessons learned.

6. Action plan. Finally, it involves developing an action plan to determine how the student will apply what he has learned to future situations or how to improve future performance based on his reflection.

We have obtained comprehensive results demonstrating the advantages of reflective learning:

Self-awareness. Reflective learning helps students gain a deeper understanding of their own strengths, weaknesses, values, and beliefs, and self-awareness helps them make more informed choices and allows you to adapt your actions to your personal and professional goals.

Improvement in approach to situational problems. By thinking more broadly and clearly about the acquired experience and previous problems, students can identify established trends that can influence decision-making processes. This understanding allows them to improve their problem-solving skills and make more effective choices in similar situations in the future.

Formed critical thinking. Reflective learning encourages students to question their own assumptions, biases, and preconceived notions, and critically examining their own thoughts and beliefs fosters intellectual growth and the ability to think critically and objectively. .

Increased empathy and understanding. Reflective learning develops empathy by encouraging speakers to consider different perspectives and understand the impact of their actions on others. This empathic understanding improves communication skills, teamwork, and personal and professional relationships.

With a few exceptions, our results show that effective reflective learning strategies are:

Keeping a diary. Keeping a thought journal allows people to regularly record their thoughts, feelings, and experiences. This practice serves as a basis for reflectivity and helps identify enriched trends for improvement.

Directed inquiry. Ask the student, "What did I learn from this experience?" or "How could I have handled this situation differently?" Asking thought-provoking questions can stimulate deep critical thinking and increase reflexivity.

Seek feedback. Actively seeking feedback from others, such as experts, students, or managers, can provide valuable insight and analytical approaches from different perspectives. This feedback can be used to highlight your strengths and areas for improvement.

Creating an educational society. Participating in discussions with experts or joining a reflexive study group can create an environment conducive to sharing experiences and ideas, and gaining new perspectives.

Reflective learning is a powerful tool that enables people to learn from their experiences, increase self-awareness, and enhance personal and professional growth. By actively engaging in self-reflection, people can gain valuable information, challenge assumptions, and make more informed decisions. Incorporating reflective learning practices into our lives can lead to continuous improvement and a deeper understanding of ourselves and the world around us.

Ta’lim jamiyatini yaratish. mutaxassislar bilan munozaralarda qatnashish yoki reflektiv o’quv guruhiga qo’shilish tajriba va fikr almashish, yangi istiqbollarga ega bo’lish uchun qulay muhit yaratishi mumkin.

In conclusion, our study has led us to conclude that reflektiv ta’lim odamlarga o’z tajribalaridan o’rganish, o’z-o’zini anglashni oshirish, shaxsiy va kasbiy o’sishni yaxshilash imkonini beradigan kuchli vositadir. O’z-o’zini aks ettirishda faol ishtirok etish orqali odamlar qimmatli ma’lumotlarga ega bo’lishlari, taxminlarga qarshi chiqishlari va ko’proq asosli qarorlar qabul qilishlari mumkin. Reflektiv ta’lim amaliyotlarini hayotimizga kiritish doimiy takomillashtirishga va o’zimizni va atrofimizdagi dunyoni chuqurroq tushunishga olib kelishi mumkin.

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